

Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-Economic Impact

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ABSTRACT: In Afghanistan, day to a day power struggle, rampant corruption, and numerous challenges increased and affected National Unity Government. The survival of the country was managed with the help of International Assistance. Afghanistan Analyst Network reports that mismanagement and electrical fraud exist in the parliamentary and presidential elections of 2018 and 2019. Two parties in Afghanistan had created continuous political tension in the country. In several ways, the government of Afghanistan suffered due to violence and insecurity problems. The socio-political management was of the country not focused on efficiently maintaining security problems.

Additionally, due to the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, ninety per cent of the Afghan people were suffering from economic, environmental crises and insecurity problems. The parliamentary election scheduled after the first election in 2004 led to several challenges due to slow preparations. The people of Afghans prefer to have a strong government was the lesson learnt by the presidential election in Afghanistan. The irregularities and fraud reveal the different types of voting patterns. The challenges of a presidential election in Afghanistan based on the voter turnout were examined in this study. The post-conflict state of the country caused the increase or decrease in voter turnout in Afghanistan. The change in the socio-political and economic, and security situation of the country was analyzed during the presidential and parliamentary elections. Parliamentary chambers of Afghanistan held over various years were analyzed based on the number of registered voters, ballots and valid votes. The stakeholder, private sector, and civil society representatives' interactions with government officials were carried out with the help of a parliamentary session consisting of a series of interactive datasets.

KEYWORDS: Election, Vote, Afghanistan, Economic, democracy, Politics,

INTRODUCTION

International assistance in Afghanistan helps manage challenges caused by rampant corruption, a weak economy and power struggle. In 2018 and 2019, the presidential elections were headed by President Ashraf Ghani and Abdullah, chief executive officer. According to the Afghanistan analyst network, mismanagement of electoral fraud was found in parliamentary elections. In Kabul, by 2020, two parallel inaugurations were held for two rival presidents. The conflict in Afghanistan needs a mediator from the international to address the conflict. In 2021, the Afghan government was challenged by insecurity, and violence increased in many ways. The socio-political situation has become affected drastically, and the country's security remains a question mark. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, economic and environmental crisis, and increasing insecurity problem in the country rises ninety per cent of the country poverty rate.

In 2004, the first presidential election in Afghanistan occurred using the electoral process (Byrd 2016; Coburn 2016; Johnson 2020; Sahar 2014). In presidential elections, voter turnout varies from country to country with a different pattern. The political factors and changes produce a significant impact on the growth of the economy. From one election to another, the way of voter turnout changes in Afghanistan. In the electoral history of Afghanistan, the electoral process was counted with less than twenty per cent votes (Ibrahmi, 2020). The output of the electoral process was not considered as a final decision. Various factors in the election, such as legitimacy and acceptability of the polls, decide the final decision of the election's success. The most crucial cause for voter turnout in Afghanistan in parliamentary elections was a complex ethnic and social division with high political stakes. The economic consequences for the country depended on the decision taken on election day. The elected government gain legitimacy and has to abide by the fundamental conditions of representative democracies (Park 2009; Smith 2017; Sanz 2015).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study targets comprehending the Democratic Election Procedures in Afghanistan and the impact on society and the economic culture by comparing the Presidential & Parliamentary Elections.

1. To distinguish variations between Presidential and Parliamentary Election Procedures in Afghanistan.

Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

2. To assess the Historical & Cultural differences between the different election types.
3. To measure Socioeconomic and Ethno-regional factors influencing the administrative framework, system, and procedures of both kinds of elections.
4. To motivates the inhabitant to be more eager & strongly ingrained during election procedures with the purpose of appropriate applicant selection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The influence of Afghanistan's electoral arrangement on the country's stability.

Reynolds (2006) has described that democracy offers provision in making a country stable when authenticity and legal enactment are ascertained. Democratic governance systems play a massive role in maintaining the nation's safety and creating issues among several shareholders owing to the permissibility of policy-making procedures.

It has been seen that the nation's safety with the aid of eagerness and issues among several shareholders in the policy-making process. For the intent to deliver an appropriate operational mechanism coupled with democratic stability, well-known legitimacy and legal regulation play a significant contribution. Using Afghanistan cases, this paper has pinpointed fundamentals and lucid organization related to democratic organization and election procedures. It has been investigated the future stability in connection with electoral rules influence. It has been purposed that the election system of Afghanistan could result in a portion of the cultural arena and an ineffective well-known presentation in the assembly of Parliament for inhibiting the effective policy making. Moreover, law rules are infringed owing to illegal wiretaps in the election process. This, in turn, leads to the impairment of mechanisms of democracy.

Elaboration of differences in Afghan Vote Participation Rates during Presidential Elections

Amin (2020) has stated that the average assessment concerned voter participation across presidential elections in Afghanistan. It leads to the examination of issues in the context of the pattern of turnout, and it also describes how the pattern has been developed. Fundamentally, it has showcased the reduction in the year of 2009 and 2019 presidential elections.

Claimants assert that Afghanistan act as a post-war state. It has been observed that a considerable measure of organizational elaboration on the voting outcome is shown to rise or decline the level of turnout. It has become vital to investigate several other essential elements that could impact the turnout of the Afghanistan elections results. Therefore, it has been evaluated that in Afghanistan, every four presidential voting's offers unexceptional elements involving turnout and some aspects of the election

Consequently, this current study has determined the correlation between a reduced number of voters and alteration in financial, the socio-political and safety scenario before the votes. Moreover, it is speculated that the obligatory president and the incompetency of authorities to make a positive impact on the life of millions of individuals, Likewise, the proposition has investigated public discontentment with the obligatory authority and discovered that turnout is influenced by fundamental dissatisfaction to a greater extent. This discontentment could be linked to the democratic system and organization procedure, the obligatory authorities and the president.

The devastation of Afghan democracy leads to Safety arrangements in Elections

Condra et al., (2019) stated that evolving level of democracy leads voting to be promoted as a means for the process of the Democratic system. It has been seen that crime is not only responsible for dramatically impacting the election, but its city inhabitants frequently observed it as fraudulent towards the safe forces for the purpose to fight against crime. There are several influences have been evaluated for these safety considerations. Ballot stations with a similar background of crime before the elections is unknowingly acquired from the various strategic position of the Afghan Police in the year 2010 Afghan parliament voting's leads to enable the recognition of police attempts. By utilizing the information from global polling websites and several investigations, it has been evaluated to a decline in Police presence by 30 per cent. The outcome of several procedures that are competing with each other for affecting the turnout of safety forces. And it reflects upon the conduct that was not operated by voters' participation to deal with crime on voting day. It has emphasized a trap for government authorities' creation through the election process in states of institutionalized and conflict pruned

Anticipation of Afghan woman in Politics

Ibrahim and Mussarat (2014) stated that females were being granted a lower position in politics as politics were regarded as a specialized area for the male only. The female contribution was confined to the reproduction process in earlier times. The major target of this paper was to elaborate on the political anticipation concepts and target females for political anticipation. In the paper, a prime was associated with the investigation of Afghanistan's female empowerment. This research emphasizes the 2014 year presidential elections which possess the role of the Afghan female. This has to turn out to be worthwhile results in the election process of 2014 after raising the rights for Afghan females. Several investigations have been utilized for the prediction of the current scenario of Afghan females by raising its contribution to the complete entire political anticipation. The major concern was linked

Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

with little discussion has been done due to female participation in the presidential election so, present research would examine the reasons and traditions to confine the female choosing the opted offices and members along with prospective scenario for afghan female.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the prime variations between Presidential and Parliamentary Election Procedures in Afghanistan?
2. What Historical & Cultural differences are observed between presidential and Parliamentary Elections?
3. What socioeconomic and ethnic regional elements influence the Political framework, system, and procedures of both election types?
4. How could the nation promote inhabitants to be more eager & strongly ingrained in Electoral procedures for the appropriate applicant selection?

DATA COLLECTION & DATA ANALYSIS

The research paper mainly relies on the documents available in either electronic or printed form. The secondary sources will consist of books, research reports and articles, and scientific commentaries available on line or in printed form. The researcher also has utilized websites of television channels and newspaper, particularly those from Afghanistan including the Tolo News, Express, Journal and magazine such as Afghanistan times Daily, The Kabul times, ICG etc. The collected secondary data has been analyzed qualitatively through Critical Analysis of Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact. This research also critically analyzed the gap between theory and practice has been investigated from the Afghanistan Election policy analysis. The diverge and converge of interests, political challenges and their solution.

METHODOLOGY FOR THE RESEARCH STUDY

This study revolves around the comprehension of Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact. For this, comparative study has been conducted between the Presidential & Parliamentary Elections. In order to meet the several objectives, secondary sources like online platform of science direct, research gate and etcetera will be used to acquire relevant papers associated with research of democratic election process in Afghanistan across the parliament and presidential elections. During study, qualitative analytic strategies will be utilized like content and discourse analysis for analysis of social and economic influence of Democratic election procedures. This research involves with qualitative methods of research in which data collection procedures like expert interviews of focused group will be conducted. Interview process will be carried out to evaluates the cultural and historical variations between presidential and parliaments judiciary system. Also, interviewed citizens' concerns linked with election process will be notified for the purpose to encourage them for voting. In addition, various official historical records consisting of IEC (Independent Election Commission), Independent election observation mission of OSCE and IEEC (Independent Electoral Complaint Commission) will be used for some defining essential factors linked to determine the difference between Parliament and presidential election process.

INTRODUCTION

There is no denying the connection between a country's political system and its level of development in all spheres of society and the economy. Governing bodies are notoriously hard to quantify (beyond simple dichotomies like "Democracy" vs. "Autocracy"), and the underlying causal relationships among these characteristics are complex. The widespread belief is that less corruption occurs in more robust democracies, hence allowing for the free and open growth of technological innovation and economic prosperity (Rivera-Batiz, 2002). Fair governments throughout the world should be able to lift their people out of poverty and unleash their full potential if their countries have a high enough per capita income. It has been argued that it is not democracy per se but rather the efficiency of government institutions that contributes to a country's overall social and economic development (Pereira and Teles, 2011). The economic rules that individuals must follow, including all necessary restrictions and all possible incentives, are set by governments.

Economic expansion and the level of material well-being enjoyed by the populace are influenced by the laws that govern investment, property rights, and other similar topics. Yet, it is also feasible that a thriving democracy might take root and thrive as a result of the social and economic progress that comes with it. Indicators of a country's social and economic health, which may contribute to the spread of democracy include the quality of its schools, the safety of its streets, and the size of its middle class (Lipset, 1959). It is said that a democracy can only function well in countries where the average citizen has a comfortable level of life, and that a society comprised of a rich few and a poor majority is doomed to fail under either oligarchy or tyranny (Lipset, 1959).

People need to be educated enough to vote and understand the issues at stake in the political process. Furthermore, historical evidence suggests that political regimes are more prone to shift during times of sluggish economic expansion. When citizens are unhappy with the state of the economy and society at large, they can go to the ballot box or the streets in order to urge their

Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

government to make changes. Luo (2020) opined that if we can put numbers to these ideas, we may get insight into the history and future of a country by studying its level of democracy and its social and economic progress. Since these studies have the ability to provide light on the global situation, they are of paramount importance. Democracy and human progress seem to go hand in hand, but it is not clear which way the causation runs. Hence, this chapter has focused on gathering theoretical knowledge on the subject matter of socio-economic impact of democratic election process from scholarly literature.

The Afghan Electoral System

The electoral process followed by Afghanistan can be said to have come into existence due to the transition that took place within the nation. Which made the democratic government be applied within the nation. The election system was made possible with the consent of the majority of people who have used the majoritarian formula as that would enable the country to follow a definite order to regulate the country. Later in the year 2004, the Afghan interim government on the recommendation of Hamid Karzai made use of this system to get the first election of the country conducted (JEMB, 2004). Ever since the day of initiation of this formula, it has continued to be the mainstream formula that guides the Afghanistan Independent Elections Commission so that they can further interpret the guidelines to select or choose the deserving winner of the Presidential election held after every five years within the nation.

The Presidential Election of 2019

The fourth and most recent election that was held in the year 2019 deals with the center of the study based on which the assumptions are made. This poll was conducted on 28th September. This year the turnout level was marked to be low. In this election, there were about 16 hopefuls who were competing for the post. Although some of the aspirants removed their names from the post before the final day of the election yet the incumbent and the two rivals continued to remain to fight for the position of power (Ramani, 2019). The major fundamental issue that remained in this process is the changes that took place in the United States Policy which was made to deal with the Afghans. Another significant issue that has been marked in this phase was the widespread corruption and the sense of mistrust that grew within the people which made them back off from participating in the election. The turnout patterns of the voters during the presidential election of Afghanistan are considered to be unique since it keeps varying from one election to another.

In this election, the winning party received 50.6% which was backed by widespread corruption practices. These studies matter because they have the ability to provide light on the global situation. Unfortunately, it is not simple to understand the direction of causation between democracy and human progress. In this pattern, the turnout was considerably lower than that of the 2014 election (Mccarthy, 2019). When planning an electoral system, one must decide whether to use single-member plurality (SMP) districts or multi-member districts in an effort to achieve proportional representation (PR). Other types of accountability are more deliberative, and they rely on the public pressing their representatives for explanations of their shifting attitudes and actions (Constable, 2019). In this election, the technical form of voting and evaluation of the vote was made having considered the ethnic bloc voting system. Thus, the trend was found to be prominent and measurably easier to be evaluated.

Major factors affective turnout in Afghanistan

According to Johnson (2018) observation, the initiatives taken in the presidential election of the year 2014 marked a systematic result. After having studied the data put forward by IEC and polling centers the irregularity in the results of the vote was witnessed. The author of the paper further elaborates on the factors that impacted the turnout in Afghanistan. The author of the paper has also put special emphasis on the issues that the people got to encounter on the day of the election and during the post-election period which gradually led the country to witness another major Civil War. The research paper further discusses the historical factors that made the country head towards the transition towards building a democratic government. The electoral fraud, ballot-stuffing, intimidation and vote-buying system practiced in the 2014 election can be considered to be the major reasons that affected the turnout in Afghanistan.

Coburn (2016) in his paper about the turnout in Afghanistan stated that Afghanistan has been in the news for the emerging trends regarding the post-electric period. The author has thus conducted an ethnographic investigation that discusses the major district located in Afghanistan's capital state. This particular district demonstrates an analysis of the nexus that takes place between democratization and elections. This author has followed a distinctive approach to analyze the factors that led to turning out in Afghanistan having taken into consideration the bottom-up system which unveils the trends that took place during the election of 2001. This author tries to focus on the local factors unlike that of most of the researchers since having looked into the local level presentation the paper gets to showcase the opportunities that enable a person to discuss the power distribution as well as the resources that were captured by the local political bodies. The research paper presented by the author has thus focused on the issues caused during the election and its impact on the vote turnover in Afghanistan and how such factors predominantly impacted the voter turnout of the country.

Coburn (2016) further comes up to discuss the case of the Qara Bagh District which falls within Kabul. In this district, the people of the place got to participate in six different types of elections to ensure that they were ready to welcome the process of

Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

democratization. The turnout patterns of the voters during the presidential election of Afghanistan are considered to be unique since it keeps varying from one election to another. However, when looking into the research materials gathered from amongst the local voters of the place it was found that there was an intense sense of dissatisfaction among the voters as they felt to have been under control. The major cause of such a situation was the intentions of the jihadi commanders and the local warlords to solidify their control on the major institutions of the government by having gained sufficient wealth so that they strengthen their impact on the process of the electoral. Furthermore, the author has put forward relevant evidence to argue that the local political elites have focused on solidifying their hold by extending their networks with respect to the patronages so that they can monopolize the resources that were available to them.

The factors that influenced the voter turnout have been further explained in the description below:

Security: Afghan has been a country that encourages post-conflict gets to face major challenges to making the country develop and grow. However, to ensure the growth of the country it is required to provide security to the people living in it in terms of both personal and individual citizens. Ever since the Taliban regime transitioned within the nation the issues with the security of the citizens have revived. Before the emergence of the Taliban security issues remained in the nation however, after the transition took place the degree to which the citizens felt insecure and threatened have hiked to a considerable level throughout the period of the election (Amin, 2019). Although the security force was deployed by the Afghan government to deal with the causes that threatened the lives of the citizens; the international security forces made sure that they get to assign the Afghans security by having put forward some operations yet the government failed to take necessary steps to provide the required security to the people living within the nation.

As per the Downsian Rational Choice, the approach to measuring the marginal cost vs marginal benefits of the problems faced by the nation to deal with the security of the people can be asserted. The issues of the citizen with respect to their security thus can be stated to be the major factor that enabled the candidates to stay away from the citizen and not appear to cast their vote on Election Day. Thus, it further ends up exceeding the marginal benefits for the participants at the time of voting. However, the Downsian Rational Choice Model put forward by Scott (2000) further justifies this action of the participants as that makes them have the choice to prefer not voting in order to maintain their safety. Voting being an arbitrary performance which prioritises the expectations and performance of the voters to cast their vote is calculated having used this particular model.

When looking into history, the 2004 elections of the nation can be found to have gone through major life-threatening events. The target attacks were made to be common that impacted the turnouts of the nation. The security threats intimidated the participation of the individuals. The citizens felt life-threatening issues in order to cast their votes. The parties involved in the election tried to convey the interests of the candidates by having made them take part in the voting process with the help of threats (Panda 2014). The second presidential election of the nation got to witness the same condition however this election turnout was found to be the most as compared to all the other elections held within the nation since it made the citizen having relied on the government operations came out of their houses to cast their votes. Although the Taliban did not step back from raping up their attacks against the government compounds to create an obstacle in the election process. The issues of the citizen with respect to their security can be taken into account to be the major factor that enabled the candidates to stay away from the citizen to ensure that they get to maintain their safety factors. Thus, this particular factor can be considered to be an integral part of the voter turnout that has been taking place within the nation over the past three elections.

Satisfaction with Democracy & Incumbent Government: Another variable that can be considered to be an essential part of the election process is satisfaction with democracy. From various group studies and data gathered from reliable sources, it can be found that about 70% of the citizen of the nation were dissatisfied with the form of democracy followed by the nation. The outrage that takes place pre and post elections grew a sense of fear and insecurity among the citizen of the nation (Mal, 2020). Some articles also suggest that the major cause had led to the formation of dissatisfying democracy was the government's failure in the post-Bonn Afghanistan policy that was executed to develop democratic institutions within the nations so that the citizens could value it. An Afghan Political Activist in an interview stated that the primary cause of the issue of voter turnout was the transition that took place in the conversion of the democratization process (Sarwary 2020). In the interview, the political activists further mentioned that in order to integrate the values of the institutions by way of getting involved in the traditional form of multicultural society the government failed to take into consideration the other vital needs of the citizens that would make the nation have greater scope to be created.

The 2004 presidential election marks the highest turnout as the total amount of ballots that were cast was eight million which was subsequently reduced by 39% in the election that took place in 2009. The major cause of this decline was the growing sense of dissatisfaction amongst the citizen. The focused group of the nation further expressed dissatisfaction with the incumbent president Karzai's performance in the administration process (Tolo News 2015). The then-former employee of the Independent Elections Commission and a political activist Najibullah Ikrami explained that the incumbent presence of the nation made the voters be higher dissatisfied with the choice as his ability to adopt changes to bring in positive change within the nation ended by getting the nation

Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

in a grave situation and further growth in the degree of insecurity in the near future (Ikrami, 2020).

The Presidential Election held in the recent past in the year 2019 can be considered an incident when the President's approval rating started to fall as soon as the National Unity Government was initiated to be established. As most of the people were found to be unsatisfied with the performance of Dr Ashraf Ghani and Dr Abdullah, they ended up voting out the members (Ahmadyar and Osmanzoi 2016). The major cause of the decline was the growing unemployment rate and the decline in financial status which further ended up paving way for mistrust of the people of the government and its working process. Thus, it can be asserted that dissatisfaction has been an integral factor that impacted the employee turnout in Afghanistan.

Electoral Malpractice

This factor is also known to be a constant factor that has been prevailing in every election held in Afghanistan. Ever since the election took place in the action the irregularities have been higher than the past election. The last three elections have witnessed a higher degree of electoral malpractice. The reports suggest that the major factor of the dissatisfaction of the voters with the election results and the process has been electoral malpractices. The decline in the number of voters has also been a major factor that makes the candidates have a smaller number of voters voting for the election. However, as per the opinion of the majority members of the focused group of the nation, electoral malpractice has been a matter of myth while a small number of focused group members accepted the fact that electrical malpractice existed. Although there have been mixed opinions regarding electoral malpractice to be the major cause of the drop in voters lists yet it continues to be an indirect factor that leads to many other factors that are directly linked to the election process.

A conflict impacts the state by having created a weak governing body. Since Afghanistan has had major issues in dealing with the insecurity and incumbent government the people found it hard to rely on the new policies that were imposed by the governing body. The people grew a higher sense of mistrust in their minds which made them do away with the turnouts. The manipulation worked in the nation at different levels as the participants of the vote enabled the citizen to vote in a biased manner as that would have impacted their lives. Fraud and misconduct have been common during the election as the malpractices further impacted the nation in being able to gain the trust of the voters. Talking about the wide perspectives of the international reviewers it can be found to have been tagged as a fraud presidential run-off election process. The incumbent government have been highly corrupt thus the sense of dissatisfaction grew within the citizen as it further impacted the individual performance of the candidates who have been on the list of the electoral list. The incumbent government encouraged the election participants to make use of electoral malpractices to win the election. Thus, the citizen showed greater interest in voting out the President rather than having cast their votes in favour of either of the government.

Influence of Afghanistan's Electoral Arrangement on the Country's Abilities

Nagl (2022) opined that the ability of the country can be asserted from the process in which the Electoral arrangements are made. The Presidential elections in the country are carried forward in a process of the two-round system so in case the candidates fail to achieve the target of 50% they can further put into the process to determine the majority vote from the voters. The second round of the election process happens to be simpler as only two of the candidates are made to step ahead for this part so that the voters can have a clear idea about who they should be voting for. This way the election process is executed so that the federal system of election can be made successful. Abjorensen (2019) came up with the opinion that the candidates are given the freedom to exercise their power to campaign for the election so that they get to reach out to the voters and state their agenda for the election; this way both the candidates and the ones voting for the election process are able to ascertain the factors that they should prioritize and further choose the president of their choice. The agenda of the country to establish the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan was initiated with the first phase of the election thus with this the country's electoral arrangement was effectively brought in.

Mebane Jr et al (2022) stated that the Constitution of the nation was set up as per the presidential system as the president who has been elected was given a wide range of powers to access the citizen. The president was elected to serve for a period of five years which was made based on the two-term limit put forward under Article 62 along with two vice presidents. However, under Article 64 the President had been given the power to select the members for high-ranking officials including the members of the Supreme Court, district governors, and provincial governors and of cabinet ministers. Bincof (2020) explained that a specific number of advisers were appointed to advise the president on important matters. Out of all the members the chief of staff was considered to be the most important member of the team as the President took this decision into consideration. There were 259 seats for the members of the National Assembly of Parliament of Afghanistan. These members were elected for the constitution of the lower house which is also known as the house of people. The division of the seat was done by having allocated 10 seats to the nomads of Kuchi, and 102 seats to the upper seat.

Jabeen and Shauket (2019) highlighted the fact that as the electoral process worked effectively the nation was able to carry out its socio-economic factors effectively. Thus, to ascertain the nature of electoral competition, the number of parties, the cohesion or fracturing of the political scene, and the ability to form a government, the selection of an electoral system has a substantial effect on the functioning of the representative democracy within the nation. The outcome of a standard form of parliamentary system was

Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

such that the disarmament of private and intense commanders who were regarded as significant ethnic factions lead to the control of the increasing cultivation of poppy as it was one of the most profitable businesses practiced by the nation. There is an important debate on whether a kind of voting system, a majority system or a proportional system, is more suitable for a society that is split down the middle. Thus, the nation executes its electoral system in a manner that the members get to cast their votes in a peaceful manner. Thus, these initiatives of the nation towards the election process made the nation create a system that can be reliable and help it to develop further.

Darnolf and Smith (2019) added that the Afghan constitution ensures that the judicial system of the nation gets to be practiced independently so that they can carry out the business effectively. Although the President ensures that each member of the judiciary is selected by the President yet after the completion of the selection process the judiciary members are given the liberty to look after the laws and order in an effective manner without having been influenced by any other wing of the Constitution of the Nation. In war-torn countries like Afghanistan, popular democratic elections provide average citizens with the opportunity to exercise their rights and choose who will represent them in government. Network and Adili (2018) put forward the point that the Presidential elections that were deemed to have the highest turnout and the least amount of carnage witnessed a diverse rate of turnout as the number of voters kept on changing with the passing time and with that the change in the political scenario of the country. Parliamentary and provincial election forms made the country consider the opinion of the people living in it so that a democratic form of government can be successfully executed within the nation. The capacity and aptitude of a citizen for participation in the political decision-making process are referred to as civic capacity, regarded as an individual attribute of the people living in Afghanistan.

As it can be asserted from the other points mentioned in the paper the Afghanistan Electoral Arrangement states the ability of the country both in terms of its domestic as well as international development. Pilster (2020) explained by stating that the candidates as well as the voters during the election are given the freedom to exercise their power to campaign for the election and to vote for the candidate of their choice; this way both the candidates and the ones voting for the election process are able to ascertain the factors that they should prioritize and further choose the president of their choice. A specific number of advisers were appointed to advise the president on important matters. This author tries to focus on the local factors unlike that of most of the researchers since having looked into the local level presentation the paper gets to showcase the opportunities that enable a person to discuss the power distribution as well as the resources that were captured by the local political bodies. However, there are some scholars who suggest that the major cause had led to the formation of dissatisfying democracy was the government's failure in the post-Bonn Afghanistan policy that was executed to develop democratic institutions within the nations so that the citizens could value it.

CONCLUSION

To vote for the leaders was the lesson the people of Afghanistan learned during the presidential election. Afghanistan's government and elections commission have found so many ways and made a continuous effort for the voters to cast their vote by ensuring safety and security. The challenges caused during the elections were efficiently handled with the help of urgent actions by the government. Ensuring security in all possible ways was considered the most challenging task for the election commission. Sufficient robust precautions were taken by the international community and by the government to address the issue. Some of the problems in the elections forced to postpone the elections in some parts of Afghanistan. Afghanistan's political transition has been conducted to ensure safety and security for the people in all district boundaries of Afghanistan. Sufficient financial resources were provided to the international community and the Afghan government. The increasing insurgency and weak institutions were considered significant challenges faced by the people of Afghanistan during elections. The people did not properly implement many government reforms due to political situations. On the other hand, the other major threat to the Afghan people was caused by the Taliban. The capacity of state institutions was affected majorly by corruption, nepotism and clientelism caused by improper management of politicians of Afghanistan. The problem of sin is considered the root cause of all illegal activities in Afghanistan. The increased poverty and internal displacement affect most people in Afghanistan. The process held in the Wolesi Jirga was considered widespread fraud. The future of Afghanistan was notwithstanding due to the criticality of a successful election. Democracy of the country was laid in the hands of the people by choosing of right representative. The deficiency of the system caused the utility of exercises. A perfect election was considered a myth in thriving and wracked countries. In all presidential elections in Afghanistan, emerging patterns of electoral fraud to clientelist practices and pattern client relations occupy a dominant place for voter turnout. Socio-political, security and political, a higher level of public dissatisfaction was considered a significant reason for the voter turnout in presidential elections in Afghanistan.

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Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

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Comparative Study between the Presidential & Parliamentary Democratic Election Process in Afghanistan and its Socio-economic Impact

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